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Abstract Book

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Best practices for animal value chain interventions to reduce zoonotic disease spillover risks at markets and farms – the USAID STOP Spillover approach

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Background: STOP Spillover is a USAID funded program developing interventions to reduce risks associated with zoonotic disease threats. Participatory epidemiological approaches in five countries – Sierra Leone, Cambodia, Vietnam, Cote D'Ivoire, and Bangladesh - identified animal value chains, including those involving wild meat and live-bird markets (LBMs) and wildlife farms as target locations for interventions to reduce risks of zoonotic spillover. Here, we highlight best practices for the design, implementation, and evaluation of animal value chain interventions at market and farm interfaces.

Methods: Routine monitoring and evaluation (M&E) protocols were developed and implemented during intervention activities at animal markets and wildlife farms, including data collection on intervention milestones, activity adaptation, and global Key Performance Indicators (KPI). M&E data were managed via a centralized database, the Global Electronic Network of Monitoring and Evaluation (GENOME) and accessible to country teams and global staff for monitoring implementation and data/file storage, facilitating improvement and adaptation. To identify best practices, data were extracted from GENOME, systematically reviewed, and context-related data were logged through informal interviews with country teams. Data were thematically analyzed to determine cross-cutting best practices.

Results: M&E data revealed six global best practices for animal value chain interventions to reduce risk of zoonotic spillover. First, multi-level, multi-sectoral stakeholder engagement ensures that design and implementation of interventions retains support, incentivizes participation, and creates opportunities for sustainability. In Vietnam, multi-level government engagement enhanced community involvement, promoting localized solutions on wildlife farms. Second, evidence-based biosafety practices (including using personal protective equipment (PPE) and protocols facilitating proper use) were easily adopted as long as issues around access were addressed. In Sierra Leone, among 47 wild meat market butchers, consistent donning of PPE (aprons, nitrile gloves, and dedicated PPE clothing) ranged from 79-99%. Third, intervention evaluation paired with sampling and surveillance helps to identify practices that reduce pathogen prevalence. In Bangladesh, pre-post sampling and control market comparisons highlighted the biosafety practices most associated with pathogen risk reduction during an LBM intervention. Fourth, public-private partnerships can facilitate economically sustainable risk reductions. In Bangladesh, STOP Spillover facilitated agreements where poultry industry partners funded biosafety-focused infrastructure improvements of LBMs, in exchange for the opportunity to sell their processed poultry products in the markets. Fifth, participatory methods such as community dialogues and trials of improved practices (TIPs) ensured that new biosafety practices were acceptable and feasible. Finally, data sharing with research subjects and local stakeholders throughout implementation reinforces sustained adoption of risk reducing behaviors.

Conclusions: STOP Spillover's approach to identifying, characterizing, and evaluating zoonotic risks along the animal value chain has elucidated best practices associated with intervention success. Best practices may be applied by future stakeholders interested in developing methods to reduce risk of zoonotic spillover at animal markets and wildlife farms.

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The 2023–2024 rabies outbreak response in West Timor, Indonesia and future economic impacts

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Background

Despite clear rabies control guidelines, national/local factors may hinder responses and must be understood early in an outbreak to stimulate urgent action. We present a rapid assessment of the rabies outbreak in West Timor ('WT'; Nusa Tenggara Timur Province, Indonesia), which started May 2023 and is now widespread, including economic impacts under different future scenarios.

Methods

Teams visited Kupang city and four of six WT districts in May 2024, gathering information from human and animal health, disaster management, and community stakeholders from different administrative levels about response activities, stakeholder coordination and engagement, costs, and epidemiological data.